

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BINARY TREE AND BOOLEAN ALGEBRA CHANGING THE PARAMETER OF THE BOOLEAN EXPRESSION : A FUNCTIONAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Present paper deals with the relationship between Binary Tree and Boolean Algebra by changing the parameter of the Boolean Expression: A functional Approach alongwith the measurement of the variation in the graphs with the changing of the parameter.

Keywords : Graph, Tree, Binary Tree, Boolean Algebra.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important paper on graph theory was introduced by Euler [2] in which he solved Königsberg bridge problem. Kirchhoff [5] and Cummins [1] developed the theory of tree and discussed with their properties. Hu and Tucker [4] have searched optimal binary search tree. Harary[5] introduced graph theoretic terminology. Lu [6] discussed on avoidable & unavoidable trees. Rizzo [7] gave short proof of König's Theorem.

There are several applications related to the study of binary tree and boolean algebra into the design of decision making problems, network problems etc.

In this paper, we considered optimal binary search tree & evaluated the variation of the graphs (binary tree graph & boolean circuit graph) with the changing of the parameter of boolean expression. This problem is useful to variety of solutions related to the tree & circuit problems.

1.1 Preliminaries

To review some definitions of Graph, Tree with properties.

A graph $G = (V, E)$ consists of a set of objects $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots\}$ called vertices, and another set $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots\}$, whose elements are called edges such that approximately an edge e_k is identified with an unordered pair (V_i, V_j) of vertices.

A tree is connected graph without any circuit with the following properties :-

- A. T is connected and circuitless.
- B. T contains 'm' vertices & 'm-1' edges.
- C. There is exactly one and only one path between every pair of vertices in T.

2. BINARY TREE

2.1 Definition

Binary Tree is a special class of rooted tree and follows the properties of tree. It is defined as a tree in which there is exactly one vertices of degree two and each of the remaining vertices is of degree one or three.

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Figure-1: for $T_B(9,8)$

Figure-2 : for $T_B(5,4)$

2.2 Observations

- (a) The number of vertices 'm' in a binary tree is always odd.
- (b) Let 'n' be the number of pendant vertices in a binary tree. Then (m-n-1) is the number of vertices of degree three. Therefore, the parameters 'n' can be calculated by:

Degree of Total vertices in Binary Tree Graph = 2 x no. of edges

$$\partial(V_{total}) = 2e \quad - \quad (1)$$

[As per the properties of tree, the no. of edges will be equal to (m-1).]

$$\partial(V_{total}) = 2(m-1) \quad - \quad (2)$$

$$2 \times 1 + 1 \times n + 3 \times (m-n-1) = 2(m-1) \quad - \quad (3)$$

$$2 + n + 3m - 3n - 3 = 2(m-1) \quad - \quad (4)$$

$$n = (m+1)/2$$

2.3 The Graph of binary tree of Boolean expressions

Fig.-3

(a) $R = a + (b * c + d) + (e * f)$ (5)

(Where a,b,c,d,e,f are defined as parameters)

(b) $R = (a/b) * (c + d/e)$ (6)

(Where a,b,c,d,e are defined as parameters)

3. BOOLEAN ALGEBRA

3.1 Definition

Boolean Algebra be a non-empty set with two binary operations : addition (+) and multiplication (*) & a unary operation complement ('), and two distinct element 0 & 1. The concept of Boolean Algebra is widely used to design the circuit graph.

3.2 The circuit graph by the consideration of Boolean algebra of the Boolean express

$R = a.c + a.b$ (7)

(Where a, b & c are defined as parameters)

Figure-5

Relationship between Binary tree and Boolean algebra ...

If we use equation (7) to draw graph as the concept of the binary tree graph, it will be as follows

The figure (6) is not binary tree graph as well as tree graph, since, it contains the circuit & circuit is not allowed in tree and binary tree graph.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The graphs (Figure 3 & 4) of binary tree do not contain any closed circuit graph, since, all the parameters of boolean expressions are different.

The graph (figure 5) of boolean algebra contains the closed circuit graph, since, the parameter of boolean expression is same.

It is inferred from the figures that if the parameters is same then the resulting graph will act as circuit and it will be a circuit graph and not be a binary tree graph (or tree). If the parameters are different then the resulting graph will act as binary tree graph and not be a circuit graph.

5. CONCLUSION

It is observed that if there is any relation between the parameters then it will generate the circuit graph & if there is no relation between the parameters then it will generate the binary tree graph or tree graph.

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